

Studies on 3-Amino-1,2,4-triazole

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1,2,4-Triazolo[2,3-*a*]-1,3,5-triazine-4-aryl-4-thiones (3a,b) and 5-(aroylamino)-1,2,4-triazoles (5a,b) have been synthesised by the reaction of 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole (1) with aroyl isothiocyanates. Also, 1 when reacted with cinnamitrile derivatives yields the triazolopyrimidine derivatives (6, 7a,b and 8). Treatment of 8 with carbon disulphide and formamide gives 9 and 10 respectively. Some of the compounds possess antimicrobial activity.

Reddy *et al.*,^{1,2} reported that reactions of 2-aminothiazole and benzothiazole with aroyl isothiocyanate in acetone yield *N*¹-aroyl-*N*²-[(thiazole or benzothiazole)]thiourea and the dehydrogenative cyclisation with $\text{PCl}_5/\text{POCl}_3$ yields 2-arylaminothiazole or benzothiazolo[3,2-*b*]-1,2,4-thiazolone. On the basis of these findings we were interested to carry out investigation in the area of 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole.

However, in our studies, the reaction of 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole (1) with aroyl isothiocyanate led to the formation of 1,2,4-triazolo[2,3-*a*]-1,3,5-triazine-2-aryl-4-thiones (3a,b) and 3-aroyl-amino-1,2,4-triazoles (5a,b), which were separated by column chromatography (Scheme 1). The forma-

tion of 5a,b can be explained through elimination of thiocyanic acid from 4a,b via a six-membered cyclic transition state². Mass spectra of 4a,b showed *m/z* 224 and 188 respectively.

On the other hand, when compound 1 was allowed to react with cinnamitrile derivatives³, several new triazolopyrimidines were obtained. Thus it has been found that 1 reacts with ethyl benzylidenecyanoacetate to yield 1,2,4-triazolo-1,3,4-trihydropyrimidin-2-one (6). Formation of 6 is assumed to proceed via initial addition of the ring nitrogen atom in 1 to the activated double bond of ethyl benzylidenecyanoacetate followed by cyclisation into 6^{3,4}.

Similarly, compound 1 reacted with benzylidene malonitrile, 4-chlorobenzylidenemalonitrile and ethoxymethylenemalonitrile in *n*-butanol/pyridine mixture to give 1,2,4-triazolo[2,3-*a*]-3,4-dihydro-2-amino-4-aryl-3-cyanopyrimidines (7a,b) and 1,2,4-triazolo[2,3-*a*]-2-amino-3-cyanopyrimidine (8) respectively. Mass spectrum of 7b showed *m/z* 237. Compound 8 reacted with carbon disulphide and formamide to give 9 and 10 respectively⁵.

Some of the compounds showed antimicrobial activity at MIC = 5.0 mg cm⁻³: 3a against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus* (zone of inhibition >5 mm); 5b against *P. aeruginosa* (>5 mm), *E. coli* (>7 mm), *B. subtilis* (>9 mm), *S. aureus* (>9 mm); 6 against *B. subtilis* (>7 mm), *S. aureus* (>5 mm); 8 against *B. subtilis* (>5 mm), *S. aureus* (>5 mm).

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were run on a Unicam sp-200 G spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a Varian MAT 711 spectrometer (70 eV) and nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A 60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

Formation of 3a,b and 5a,b: To a solution of ammonium thiocyanate (0.01 mol) in acetone (40 ml), equimolar quantity of aroyl chloride was added dropwise with shaking. After boiling the mixture on a steam-bath for 2 h, equimolar amount of 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole was added and refluxed for 2 h. The solvent was then distilled off and the residue treated with ice-cold water. The solid that sepa-

Scheme 1

rated was dried and purified by column chromatography : **3a** (28%), m.p. 294° (MeOH); ν_{\max} 1 570 (C=N), 1 280 (C=S), 3 300 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 7.5–8 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 8.5 (1H, s, CH triazole); **3b** (22%), 179° (MeOH); ν_{\max} 1 575 (C=N), 1 290 (C=S), 3 320 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 7.6–8.2 (4H, m, C_6H_4), 8.6 (1H, s, CH triazole); **5a** (49%), 315° (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1 680 (C=O), 1 600 (C=N), 3 340 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 7.6–8.3 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 8.5 (s, CH triazole); **5b**, (52%), 282° (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1 590 (C=N), 1 635 (C=O), 3 310 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 7.7–8.3 (4H, m, C_6H_5), 8.6 (1H, s, CH triazole).

Formation of 7a,b, 6, and 8 : A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and of **11**, **12a,b** or **13** (0.01 mol) in n-butanol-pyridine mixture was refluxed until the reaction was complete (tlc control; time range 4–10 h). The solvent was then evaporated and the remaining product was triturated with a little water and then acidified with concentrated HCl. The resulting solid products were collected and crystallised from proper solvent : **6**, (47%), m.p. 218° (C_6H_6); ν_{\max} 1 590 (C=N), 1 610 (C=O), 2 215 (C≡N), 3 340 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 3.5 (m, br, 2 × CH), 7.5–8.2 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 8.5 (s, CH triazole); **7a**, (56%), 196° (MeOH); ν_{\max} 1 580 (C=N), 2 200 (C≡N), 3 300 cm^{-1} (NH_2); δ 3.0 (2H, m, br, 2 × CH), 7.1–7.6 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 8.4 (s, CH triazole); **7b** (47%), 238° (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1 790 (C=N), 2 210 (C≡N), 3 300 cm^{-1} (NH_2); δ 3.2 (2H, m br, 2 × CH), 7.0–7.5 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 8.4 (s, CH triazole); **8** (68%), 175° (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1 570 (C=N), 2 200 (C≡N), 3 300 cm^{-1} (NH_2); δ 8.2 (1H, pyrimidine), 8.5 (1H, s, CH triazole).

Formation of 9 : A solution of **1** (1 g in 20 ml dimethylformamide) was added to a mixture of CS_2 (10

ml) and trimethylamine (2 ml). The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for 10 h, the solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue dissolved in NaOH solution (10%; 20 ml). The solution was acidified with acetic acid, the solid product was filtered off, dried and crystallised from benzene, (58%), m.p. 187°, ν_{\max} 1 270 (C=S), 1 580 (C=N), 3 310 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 8.1 (1H, pyrimidine), 8.6 (1H, s, CH triazole).

Formation of 10 : A solution of **8** (0.01 mol) in formic acid and dimethyl formamide (5 ml of each) was refluxed for 9 h. The mixture was then cooled, the solid product dried and crystallised from benzene, (53%), m.p. 232°; ν_{\max} 1 590 (C=N), 3 340 cm^{-1} (NH_2); δ 8.3 (2H, 2 × CH pyrimidine), 8.5 (1H, s, triazole).

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